

Change In The Prevalence Of Anemia From The Year 2005 To 2021

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Abstract

Anemia is the condition of the body where the number of the Red Blood Cells decreases in the body and is unable to meet the physiological needs of the body. The function of the RBCs is to deliver oxygen from the lungs to the tissues and carbon dioxide from the tissues to the lungs. This is accomplished by using haemoglobin (Hb), a tetramer protein composed of haem and globin. Anemia reduces the oxygen carrying capacity of the body due to decrease in the number of red blood cells. The recent NFHS 5 survey has shown increased percentage of the people suffering from anemia when compared to the NFHS 4 survey data. There are several factors that are being considered for the increase in the percentage like lack of formal education, poor financial status, socio-cultural differences, inadequate diet etc. Despite the running of the anemia mukt bharat programme the numbers still remains high. This forces us to identify the gaps in the running anemia eradication plans and fill them to achieve success.

Keywords

Anemia, Anemia Mukht Bharat, Iron Deficiency

Introduction

Anemia is a condition where the body doesn't have enough healthy red blood cells or hemoglobin to carry oxygen to the body's tissues. Anemia affects approximately 1.62 billion people worldwide, accounting for a quarter of the world's population (approximately 25%). Anemia results from one or more of the following process: defective red cell production, increased red cell destruction or blood loss. Iron is necessary for synthesis of hemoglobin. Iron deficiency is thought to be the most common cause of anemia globally, but other nutritional deficiencies (including folate, vitamin B12 and vitamin A), acute and chronic inflammation, parasitic infections, and inherited or acquired disorders that affect Hb synthesis, red blood cell production or red blood cell survival can all cause anemia. Iron deficiency anemia results in impaired cognitive and motor development in children and decreased work capacity in adults. The effects are most severe in infancy and early childhood. In pregnancy iron deficiency anemia can lead to perinatal loss, prematurity and low birth weight (LBW) babies. Iron deficiency anemia also adversely affects the body's immune response. (*Guidelines for control of Iron deficiency anemia, 2013*)

Objective of study

The objective of the study was to analyse the trend of anemia among the Indian population from the NFHS 3 to NFHS 5.

Review of Literature

Abhijit et al., (2004): This study presents data of National Family Health Survey (NFHS) data of 2019-2020 that indicates that prevalence of anaemia among children aged 6-59 months that is 67.1%, while among women aged 15-49 years, it is 57%. These figures highlight the significant burden of anaemia in India. This number has increased from 2015-16 to 2019-21.

Singh et al., (2022): This study represents prevalence of anaemia among men. It is a significant health issue which has not been given due importance. Only a handful of studies have captured the prevalence of anaemia among men. There is dearth of evidence base on anaemia among men in India. Therefore, this study attempts to fill this research gap by examining the socioeconomic, geographic, health-related, and behavioural differentials of anaemia among rural men in India.

Chakrabarty et al., (2023): This study aimed to analyse the change in the prevalence of anaemia among adolescent women in India from 2015 to 2021 and identify the factors associated with anaemia in this population. This study used information on 116,117 and 109,400 adolescent women (aged 15-19) from the fourth and fifth round of National Family Health Survey, respectively. Bivariate statistics and multivariable logistic regression were employed to identify the statistically significant predictors of anaemia.

Main Text

Anemia in India

The prevalence of anemia in India remains high in children, especially those in rural areas, and in women of childbearing age, and its impairment of neurological development can have serious lifelong effects. It is concerning that the most recent official data (2019-21) indicate an increased prevalence compared with 2015-16.(*Givens, D. Ian, Seetha Anitha, and Carlotta Giromini*)

The table below shows the trend of anemia in different age groups according the National Family Health Surveys conducted in India.

Table:2.1 Prevalence of anemia between the year 2005 – 2021(NFHS 3 to NFHS 5)

Age Groups	NFHS 3 (2005-2006) % Anemic in Residence	NFHS 4(2015-2016) % Anemic in Residence	NFHS 5(2019-2021) % Anemic in Residence
Children 6-59 months	69.5	58.6	67.1
Women 15-48 years not pregnant	53.2	53.2	57.2
Women 15-48 years pregnant	58.7	50.4	52.2
Men	24.2	22.7	25.0

(Data Source: *Givens, D. Ian, Seetha Anitha, and Carlotta Giromini. "Anemia in India and its prevalence and multifactorial aetiology: a narrative review." Nutrients 16.11 (2024): 1673*)

Definition of anemia in NFHS 3 : 2005-06 Hb children < 11.0 g/dL, women < 12; men < 13; NFHS 4: 2015-16 Hb children < 11.0 g/dL, non-pregnant women < 12, pregnant women < 11, men < 13; NFHS 5 : 2019-21 Hb children < 11.0 g/dL; non-pregnant women < 12; pregnant women < 11; men < 13.

Figure 2.1 Prevalence of anemia between the year 2005 – 2021(NFHS 3 to NFHS 5)

The data from the different NFHS Surveys conducted between the year 2005 to 2021 suggests changing trends of prevalence of anemia in India. According to the data the percentage of the children suffering from anemia, aged 6-59 years have increased from 58.6 percent in NFHS 4 to 67.1 percent in NFHS 5 but still lower than the percentage of 69.5 in NFHS 3 survey. The women of reproductive age group(not pregnant) suffering from anemia remained similar for the NFHS 3 and NFHS 4 survey i.e 53.2 but the percentage increased in the NFHS 5 survey to 57.2. The percentage of women of reproductive age group (pregnant) suffering from anemia was 58.7 percent in the NFHS -3 survey, which decreased to 50.4 in the NFHS -4 survey, but again rose to 52.2 percent in the NFHS-5 survey. The percentage of men suffering from anemia in the NFHS 3, NFHS 4 and NFHS 5 survey was 24.2 percent, 22.7 percent and 25 percent respectively.

Findings

Rationale For The Increase In The Percentage of Anemia Among Different Age Groups

Increase In Prevalence of Anemia In Children

Findings indicate that the child malnutrition is influenced by various socio-economic, nutritional, and health-related factors. All these factors play a significant role in child anaemia. However, some factors are significant, specifically, the variables, Adequate diet at birth, Severe wasting, and diarrhea being insignificant for mother’s anaemia in all three regression models. Nonetheless, they remain significant for child anaemia, making them what we refer to as “pure child-related variables”. Women who become pregnant before the age of 19 have been identified as a significant factor of women’s anaemia, whereas not being a factor in the case of child anaemia. It is a well-known fact that a woman’s anaemia can be transferred to her offspring. While some socio-economic factors may be similar in both cases, the root cause of the anemia differ significantly (Abhijit, Ghosh, et al.)

Increase In The Prevalence of Anemia In Adolescent Women

The level of education turned out to be a significant predictor of anaemia among adolescent women. Adolescent women with higher education are less likely to be anaemic than those without formal education. The findings of the study indicate that adolescent women from the ST community are more likely to be anaemic than other social groups. STs have been historically disadvantaged, challenges like lack of education, inadequate healthcare facilities, socio- cultural barriers, lack of employment and resources increased vulnerability to anemia. Better financial condition of the family led to better consumption of

nutritious meals while the poorer households with lack of financial stability showed more people suffering from anemia (Chakrabarty, Mahashweta, et al)

Increase In The Prevalence of Anemia In Men

An estimated one-fourth of Indian rural men aged 15 to 54 years were found to be anaemic. In the last four years, the prevalence of anaemia has only risen . The findings suggested that the prevalence of anaemia varies by sociodemographic characteristics among rural men. Rural men who were 49–54 years old, had no formal education, belonged to ST group, were Muslim, or from the poorest wealth quintile, lived in the eastern region, were underweight, and consumed alcohol and smokeless tobacco on a daily basis were more likely to have anaemia. (Singh, Aditya, et al)

Conclusion

The data from the National Family Health Survey suggests an increase in the percentage of children, women of reproductive age group (pregnant and non-pregnant) and the men suffering from anemia from the NFHS 4 Survey to NFHS 5 survey. The rationale for prevalence of anemia is majorly lack of education, socio-cultural differences, low economic status, lack of nutritious meals etc. Understanding and addressing these issues will help strengthen the programs like Poshan Abhiyan and Anemia Mukh Bharat. Despite of the government's efforts for eradicating anemia on the national level the numbers still remains high. The need of the hour is to identify the reason and correct the gaps in the ongoing anemia eradication plan in order to achieve Anemia Mukh Bharat.

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